

PRODUCTIVITY OF MILLET (*Pennisetum glaucum*) AND ITS MARKETING IN MAKODA LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA OF KANO STATE IN SUDAN SAVANNA ZONE, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

The experimental research was conducted at Makoda local government area of Kano State of about 41 km away from Kano metropolitan along Kano – Daura main road. 2022 rainy season's bumper harvest was used for the assessment of millet (*Pennisetum glaucum*) production and its marketing within Sudan Savanna zone of Nigeria. Makodalocal government within Kano State area experienced a yearly rainfall usually between June to October each year as mono-modalseasonal rainfall and the average mean annual rainfall of 2022 rainy season and average mean daily temperature were (760.1 mm), annual temperature ranges between (26.0 - 32°C). Bulk average mean value of sample soil from the research sites indicated sandy loam of pH 6.52, Organic matter content of 2.91 g kg⁻¹, total nitrogen of 0.69 g kg⁻¹ and available phosphorus of 20.2 mg kg⁻¹. The research study consisted for the selection of five (5) villages' heads areas out of twenty two (22) villages' heads areas in the local government territory due to numerous numbers of farmers cultivating millet crop. Villages heads' areas (wards) were selected through random sampling according to the research study as (Wailare ward made up of Yallada settlement, Wailare settlement and Satame settlement), (Jibga ward made up of Cidari settlement, Jibga settlement and Sabonruwa settlement), (Makoda ward made up of Babban - ruga settlement, Mai tsidau settlement and Dunawa settlement), (Bare – bari ward made up of Bare bari settlement, Yanbawa settlement and Korentabo Settlement), (Gawon Kadandani ward made up of Kantudu settlement), (Incikwallo settlement and Danmadaki settlement with the random selection of 30 millet farmers each of the five (5) randomly selected villages heads' wards for the research trial which made up of a total of 150 farmers (respondents). The results of the research study revealed that, there were high level of millet grains production in the study areas with low level efficiency of millet grains marketing system; the millet grains markets were centered within the production areas at local levels of consumptions also socio-economic characteristics of the respondents had significant effects on the marketing margin (profit) and several factors were identified as constraints in millet grains production and its marketing. Based on the findings of this study, it is recommended that, formation of group co-operatives in the study areas will reduce high cost of inputs purchases for annual rainy season millet production, transportations, enhance profit margin among the millet producers and henceforth will facilitate efficient linkages to many classes of millet market traders through formations of micro selling schemes, use of contract agreements and setting up of online marketing systems (digitalization) to sensitize annual domestic production levels within the study areas pending for further research findings.

Key words – Wards, harvest, Settlement, Production, Profit margin, Cooperatives, Marketing

INTRODUCTION

Millet (*Pennisetum glaucum*) is one of the most commonly cultivated specie worlds widely. It thrives well under hot and dry climatic conditions with average rainfall of 200-600 mm annually with highly saline soils where maize and potatoes recorded poor yields (Nagarajan *et al.*, 2007).

Millet is highly variable grass crop specie believed to have been originated from West African wild grasses over 40,000 years ago (National Research Council, 2006). Millet crop is identified by their small grain sizes and are considered as the fourth most important cereal crop after rice, maize, and sorghum in terms of cultivation and production in the tropics. Statistics indicated that, over 95 percent of millet production areas are concentrated in African and Asian countries (Basavaraj *et al.*, 2010). Millets forms a staple diet for over 500 million households who are mainly small-scale farmers living in arid and semi-arid lands of the poorest states of the world (National Research Council, 1996). Millet crop covers over 12 to 15 million hectares in Africa (Nigeria, Niger, Chad, Burkina Faso, Mali, Sudan and Uganda) and Asia (China and India) respectively. According to ICRISAT 1996, within the last 5 years, millet production in Africa has been on a downward trend partly due to high demand and profitability of competing crops, although, it still accounts for almost 87 percent of the total area planted with the crop.

Millet forms an excellent feed for livestock, both as grain and forage. Studies have revealed that broilers fed on Millet are heavier with better feed conversion rate than those fed on maize (Gulia *et al.*, 2007). Millet is nutritionally rich compared to other cereals; its consumption pattern has reduced significantly in the past three decades, this has been linked to its lengthy cooking time, change in consumers taste and preference, biased policies of supplying fix cereals at subsidized prices to urban consumers and the free distribution of maize seeds to small scale farmers even though they perform poorly in arid and semi-arid lands. Total hectares allocated to millet cultivation in Nigeria have reduced from 115, 302.6 in 2007 to 100,143.9 in 2011. Yield per declined from 1,610 kilograms in 1980 to 800 kilograms in 2008 against the potential yield of 1,500- 3,000 kg ha⁻¹ (KARI, 2007 and KARI, 2008). According to him, these negative trends have resulted to its imports from Tanzania and Uganda especially for industrial processing which was estimated to 1,560 metric tons annually (United States Agency for International Development (USAID, 2010). Small scale millet producers have identified several market constrains limiting millet value addition and promotional attempts. Amongst these are poorly developed and fragmented marketing channels with weak value chains, high processing costs, uncompetitive grain prices which collapses during harvesting season, low access to credit, lack of legal marketing sincere policy framework and dissolution of commodity boars among others (FAO, 1996). According to Gulia *et al.*, 2007 millet grain has no specific price and this has limited farmers' interest to its production despite to the local communities' preference of the crop.

It is necessary therefore to increase Millet marketing and value addition initiatives in order to increase its consumer demand.

According to Gok, 2012, within the last three years, the government of Nigeria has put more emphasis in promoting the usage of traditional crops and millet crop was inclusive in order to improve their acceptability and consumption which will in turn increase the small holder incomes and reduce food insecurity. In the year 1994 - 2007, the government of Nigeria in collaboration to International Fund for Agricultural Development initiated the eastern province horticultural and traditional food crops projects to improve smallholders' incomes

and food security through increased production of traditional food crops through Nigeria including millet crop (IFAD, 2017). According to Karanja *et al.*, 2009, collaborative projects among NGOs' were funded by International Crops Research Institute for Semi-arid Tropics (ICRISAT, 2008), International Sorghum and Millets Institute (INTSORMIL) together with Bill and Melinda Gates Harnessing Opportunities for Productivity Enhancement (HOPE) through these projects' interventions among which includes crops breeding and their improvements, distribution of improved varieties and promotion of resources conservation and management to address productivity and marketing challenges.

Millet (*Pennisetum glaucum*) is widely cultivated crop in India and Nepal (Upadyaya *et al.*, 2007). It is estimated that, millet crop production accounts for 11% worldwide (Basavaraj *et al.*, 2010). Under irrigated conditions, yields of up to 5-6 metric tons ha⁻¹ have been obtained. Millet has wider adaptability and higher nutritional quality (Gopalan *et al.*, 1996). Millets is a major food sources for resource to poor farmers in the semi-arid tropics, due to their ability to grow in poor soils with limited inputs (Kathari *et al.*, 2005). Four of the most important commonly grown millets are: pearl millet (*Pennisetum glaucum*), foxtail millet (*Setaria italica*), Proso millet (*Penicum milliaceum*) and millet (*Eleusin ecoracana*). The rest referred to as minor millets includes barnyard millet (*Echinochloa spp.*), Kodo millet (*Paspalum scrobiculatum*) (Obilana *et al.*, 2002). Millet productivity in the last five decades showed consistent increases. India and in African countries includes Kenya, Namibia, Rwanda, and Zaire, productivity declined substantially by up to 71% in the last decade (Gok, 2012).

Millet ranked fourth among cereal crops followed by sorghum (*Sorghum bicolor*). Pearl millet (*Pennisetum glaucum*) and foxtail millet (*Setaria italica*) can be cultivated under varied agro-climatic conditions (Dida *et al.*, 2007). In Africa it is extensively cultivated in Uganda, Kenya, Tanzania, Ethiopia, Rwanda, Burundi, Zambia and Malawi (Mnyentembe and Gupta, 1998).

Management of Millet Crop

Millet provides farmers with a reliable access to food and nutrition in environments with erratic and scanty rainfall and low soil fertility levels. This is attributed to its wide genetic adaptation and ability to grow successfully in diverse soils, varying rainfall regimes, divers photoperiods in marginal arid and mountainous terrains where major cereal have low success (Padulosi *et al.*, 2009). Despite these desirable qualities, Millet yields in Africa have steadily been declined in countries as Uganda, Ethiopia and Kenya (Oduori, 2008). Millet production's constraints in eastern Africa includes low soil fertility, environmental and nutrient stresses, pests and diseases, blast disease (*Magnaporthe grisea*), and Striga weed *Striga hermonthica* (Oduori, 2007) among other constraints. He further said that, adoption of improved varieties and management practices such as use of fertilizers could be improve. Application of NPK along with micronutrients and FYM at the rate of 7.5 - 12.5 increases yields of Millet (Obilana *et al.*, 2002), Millet is also known to benefit flora residual fertility from the previous crop. Other soil fertility replenishment approaches have been developed based on naturally available cropping systems. Babu *et al.*, (2007) reported that, direct application of indigenous phosphates rocks is potentially important to locally available phosphorus). Benefit - cost ratios indicated that, legume - millet rotations were profitable to proceeding crops (Gok, 2012).

Commercialization and Marketing Strategies of Millet grains

Increasing millet productivity and value added product development will depend on increased consumption of the crop, commercialization and its marketing. According to Tyler *et al.*, (2006) there is need to improve the processing technologies of millet crop as well as the quality of the end products. He further said that, diversification of the end use products would also enhance commercialization of the crop. Bitter presentation and package of ready to use millet products as moles and cookies will increase consumers' demands. Several studies have highlighted on the contributions of some neglected and under-utilized crops species and millet crop is inclusive towards generating income in both domestic and international markets (Basavaraj *et al.*, 2010).

Statement of the Problem

Despite the collaborates efforts done through national and international NGOs on interventions for improving traditional crops in Nigeria, information on millet marketing particularly value chain potentials, coordination, distributions and collaboration is limited or non-existence at all towards millet productivity and marketing channels in Makoda Local Government area due to existing reasons comprised of inadequate ratio of extension personal per house hold, use of traditional seeds, unavailability of improved recommended seeds, weeds infestations, poor communication networks, etc. among others.

Justification of the study

Millet is a potential alternative food crop in arid and semi-arid zones of Nigeria that provided immediate food and nutritional security to over 79 percent of food insecure to rural, semi urban and urban populace if proper cultivated and marketed, knowledge of market efficiencies provided valuable information to policy makers about the potential opportunities of improving the welfare of millet producers and marketers as well as their related activities. Analysis of millet value chain additions also helped policies makers in the identification of weak chains and entry points thereby guided to profitable production improvements, initiatives and distributions decisions. Moreover, identification of marketing channels information offered policies decision makers links millet producers to the final marketers or consumers.

Nevertheless, accepted and recommended profitable guided production procedures of millet crop could be achieve through adequate extension education, researches, improved market value chains additions strategies, efficiencies on marketings' networks enlightens campaigns coupled with justifiable successful production of the crop the study area and country at large since previous reviews have shown that, efficient coordination and combination of multiple strategies have the potentials in improving the market demands and ultimately producers' outputs.. Therefore, this study intended to assess the millet production and marketing existence in Makoda Local Government Area, Kano State of Sudan Savanna Zone in Nigeria.

Objectives of the study are: -

- To identify the socio-economic characteristics of millet producers in the study area.
- To identify problems associated to millet production in the study area.
- To identify marketing constraints associated to millet vendors in the study area.
- To assess the marketing channels' efficiencies of millet grains to consumers.
- To determine ways of increasing the profit of millet production farmers in the study area

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Population of the study

The research study was conducted at Makoda Local Government area of Kano State in Sudan Savannah zones of Nigeria. Makoda Local Government has its headquarter at Koguna town with the total land area of 5,932 and population of 152,837 which are mostly Hausa, Fulani and very few individual tribes with dominant occupation of farming activities, traditional weaving industries, trading and few civil servants. Islam is the main dominant religion in the study area with very few individual Christians. (N.P.C. 1991 Census)

Sampling Technique and Size

The research trial involved random selection of 5 villages' heads areas in Makoda LG which were regarded as blocks of agricultural extension supervisors due to their bulk millet cultivators in such areas which included (viz) Wailare ward - "Yallada settlement, wailare settlement and Satame settlement, Jibga ward - Cidari settlement, Jibga settlement and Sabonruwa settlement, Makoda ward - Babbanruwa, Mai tsidau, and Dunawa settlement, Bare - bari ward - bare bari settlement, "Yanbawa settlement and Korentabo Settlement, Gawon Kadandani ward - Kantudu settlement, Incikwallo settlement and Danmadaki settlement. The research study consisted of random selection for 30 millet farmers' each 5 villages' heads areas within the Makoda LG which made up of a total of 150 farmers (respondents) for the research trial.

Data collection and analysis

Data collected from the distributed structured questionnaires were analyzed with the aid of simple descriptive statistics (percentage) after its retrieval from the randomly selected farmers (responses) in the randomly selection manner within the study areas of the Local Government with regards to 2022 rainy season's millet production and marketing.

Results and discussions

Table 4.1: Gender distribution of participated millet farmers

Gender	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Male	84	70.00
Female	36	30.00
Total	120	100

Sources: questionnaire 2022

Table 4.1 above showed that, 70% of the farmers' population was males while 30% was females with the highest percentage of the males farmers exceeding the female farmers in the research areas signifying need to motivate female farmers in the production areas. This showed that, the percentages of females farmers has to be motivated through provision of an incentives as a motivational factor to bridge the gaps of gender differences in order to increase the millet bumper harvest in the study area and country at large as well as formation of millet females farmers' groups by extension personnel NGOs in each of the research trial areas.

Table 4.2: Age ranges of millet farmers

Age range	Number of respondents	Percentage (%)
20-30	38.4	32.00
31-40	40.8	34.00
41-60	26.4	22.00
60 - Above	14.4	12.00
Total	120	100

Sources: questionnaire 2022

Table 4.2 above showed that, 34 percentages of the respondents were within the age range of 31-40 owning to 38.4 statistical value of respondents during the research trial followed by age range of 20 – 30 with the statistical value of 32 percentage whereas age range of 60 and above being the least among others with only 12 percentage and having a statistical value of 14.4 when compared to rest of the respondents for the research indicating that, there will be an increasing millet production in the study area since an increase of youth enrolment to farming activities ensures correlated potential efforts to increase the annual production in terms of man power needed to boost millet production.

Table 4.3: Land acquisition with respect to current millet production in the study areas

Mode	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Gift	24	20.00
Inheritance	39	32.50
Purchase	42	35.00
Rent	15	12.50
Total	120	100

Sources: questionnaire 2022

Table 4.3 above showed that, persistence of millet production in the study area will be favorably be increased as 35 percentages of millet producers owned and acquired land through purchase and are having a statistical value of 42 being the highest value among the category of millet farmers in the study areas followed by 32.5 percentage with statistical value of 39 out of 120 participated farmers with the least of 12.5 percentage owned their millet production land through restages with a statistical value of 15 among other millet farmers in the study area. Highlight of this result indicated that, the millet production will continually be increased since many farmers owe land through purchase rather than gifted and restage for the sustainability of their production.

Table 4.4: Economic status of individual farmers based on their income level at the study area

Income level	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1,000 - 10,000	24	20.00
10,001-50,000	33	27.50
50,001-100,000	47	39.17
100,001-above	16	13.33
Total	120	100

Sources: questionnaire 2022

According to the table 4.4 above, 39.17 percentages of millet production farmers are having an income level between 50,001 to 100,000 followed by 10,001 - 50,000 with a

statistical frequency value of 33 while 13.33 percentages of farmers has statistical value of 16 being the highest income level farmers among the millet producers. This showed that, very few millet production farmers has higher power of production hence the need of governments and NGOs to provide interventions are paramount according to this research trial in order to increase the production of the crop through an increased income level powers of those individual millet farmers with low income levels according to the research. It also shows that, the income of farmers could be increase through agricultural soft loans and provision subsidized inputs as to boost millet production in the study areas.

Table 4.5: Production ability of individual farmers with regards to their farms sizes

Size (hectares)	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1-5 hectares	59	49.17
6-10 hectares	28	23.33
11-15 hectares	19	15.83
16 to above	14	11.67
Total	120	100

Sources: questionnaire 2022

Table 4.5 above shows that 49.17 % responses were with statistical frequency value of 59 have land for cultivation between 1 – 5 hectares and obtained the highest % followed by 23.33 % owing 6 – 10 hectares of land. Farmers having 16 hectares and above possessed only 11.67 % indicating that youth are engaging themselves in agricultural enterprise better than other vocational enterprises though their farms sizes are small for commercial agriculture which may lower their ability to accept and adopt new farm practices and innovations as income levels and larger farm sizes influences sustainable commercial agriculture (millet production).

Table 4.6: fertilizer usage

Fertilizer	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Organic fertilizer	37	30.83
In organic	22	18.33
Both	61	50.84
Total	120	100

Sources: questionnaire 2022

Table 4.6 shows that, half of the respondents out of 120 participants obtained the highest percentage of 50.84 with statistical frequency value of 61 for using both organic and in organic fertilizer during their millet cultivations followed by farmers who have uses organic fertilizers only with 30.83 % and statistical frequency of 37 among others. Farmers that utilize only inorganic fertilizer in their farms obtained 18.33 % with 22 values of statistical frequencies. These refers that, agricultural development in our society can be re uplifted since youth embraces agricultural activities at rate which indicated speedy growth of agricultural enterprises due to high enrolment percentage for used of both organic and in-organic fertilizer for profitable and commercial agricultural enterprises.

Table 4.7: Sources of planting materials (seeds)during their millet productions

Seed sources	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Village markets	28	23.33

Agric. Vendors	19	15.83
Nearby farmers	46	38.34
Previous reserved seeds	27	22.50
Total	120	100

Sources: questionnaire 2022

Table 4.7 shows that 38.34 % of the farmers obtained their planting materials from nearby farmers followed by those who obtained their planting materials from village markets and those uses previous reserved seeds for their planting owing 23.33 % and 22.5 % in which those purchased planting materials from agricultural vendors obtain the least percentage of 15.83 with statistical frequencies value of 19 that is statistically insignificant when compared to the rest farmers. This research findings indicated that, farmers purchases most of their planting materials from an open market which is not an improve varieties due to in sufficiency of extension agents coupled with non-subsidizeimproved seed prices from governments, NGOs and agricultural vendors and at end resulted up to total poor harvest and lost at the expenses of purchasing unimproved / low price seeds in the open market.

Table 4.8: Adoptable millet grains marketing channels in the study areas

Channels	Number of Sellers	Percentage (%)
Cooperative body / NGO	21	17.50
Whole sellers	25	20.83
Retailers	26	21.67
Consumers	48	40.00
Total	120	100

Sources: questionnaire 2022

Table 4.8 shows that, 40% of the farming production are consumed by the producers together with their relatives while rest 60 % of the production revealed as 21.67 % marketed by retailers, 20.83 % by whole sellers and 17.5 % disposed out by cooperative bodies / NGO. This indicated that if farmers will organize their activities through cooperatives, it will be easy for them to sell out their production outputs with aid of Google from point of the production to the point of consumption since we are now in digital era that will maximizes their profits through curtailing out transportation costs and associated risks while transporting the agricultural outputs.

Table 4.9 Sources of fertilizer for millet production in the study areas

Fertilizer sources	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Cooperative societies /NGO	21	17.50
Village open market	64	53.33
Agric. vendors	35	29.17
Total	120	100

Sources: questionnaire 2022

Table 4.9 shows that 53.33% of the farmers got their fertilizer for their rainy season production at an open market followed by 29.17% of farmers through agricultural vendors while only 17.5% purchases fertilizer from cooperative / NGO with a statistical frequency value of 21. This shows that governmental agricultural supply company and industries are highly in need to alleviate this problems and other related hardship associated to farmers towards the purchase of genuine fertilizer for their production.

Table 4.10: Mode of transportations for inputs and outputs production in the study areas

Mode	frequency	Percentage (%)
Animal track	23	19.17
Car / bus	57	47.50
Motor cycle	29	24.17
Bicycle	11	09.16
Total	120	100

Sources: questionnaire 2022

Table 4.10 shows that 47.5% of farmers used cars and buses for their transportation of agricultural inputs and outputs while 24.17% utilized motorcycles. Very few farmers of 19.17% and 9.16% used animal tracts and bicycles for their transportations. This implies that, transportation of farmers' agricultural inputs and outputs will be very easy and convenient with train though un-available and high prices of inflated petroleum / diesel resulted to increase in the cost of production leading to low profit or lost due to high transportation costs.

Summary

Millet crop is highly variable grass family crop believed to have been originated from West African wild grasses of over 40,000 years ago and its persistence commercial production and profitable marketing in studyarea could only be achieved with the adoption of the above highlighted findings.

The study revealed that, there is low level efficiency in the millet grain marketing system; the millet grain market is also concentrated at production areas rather than urban or for abroad exports. There is need for efficient linkages of all classes of millet market traders more especially through using goggle, such policies might include formation of micro selling schemes, use of contract agreements and setting up of online marketing system to sensitize annual domestic production levels and supply for profitable commercial production.

Conclusion

This study analyzed the economics production of millet and its marketing at Makoda local government area of Kano State, Nigeria. This study revealed that there is low level efficiency in millet grains marketing system; the millet grain market is also concentrated mostly at production areas; the socioeconomic characteristics of the respondents had significant effects on marketing margin (profit); and several factors have been identified as constraints in millet grains production and its marketing. It has been revealed that, production and marketing costs were relatively high due to difficulties in purchasing genuine agricultural inputs from governmental agencies and related agro – allied agencies as well as provision of accessible good road and formation of cooperative societies for worldwide goggle marketing.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made for policy actions to improve profitability and reduce marketing costs against millet grains marketers.

- i. The finding recommends formation of group cooperatives to reduce the high cost of inputs, transportation and enhance profit margin among millet producers and suppliers.
- ii. The finding recommends for the efficient linkages of all classes of millet market traders through formations of micro selling schemes, use of contract agreements and setting up of online marketing system to sensitize annual domestic production levels of the study areas and supplies world widely.

REFERENCE

- Babu B.K., N. Senthil S.M. Gomez, K.R. Biji, N.S. Rajendraprasad, S.S. Kumar and R. Chandrababu (2007) Assessment of genetic diversity among Millet (*Eleusinecoracana* (L.) Gaertn.) accessions using molecular markers. *Gen. Res. Crop Evol.* 54:299-404.
- Basavaraj, G. porthasaratly, raop. Bhagavatula s. Ahmad w. (2010) Availability and utilization of pearl millet in india. *Journal of SAT Agricultural Research* 8.
- FAO (Food and Agricultural Organization) (1996). *The world Sorghum and Millet Economics facts. Trends and outlook.*FAO Document Responsibility W1808\E.
- Gopalan C., B.V. Rama Sastri and S.C. Balasubramanian (1996) *Nutritive Value of Indian Foods.*National Institute of Nutrition, Indian Council of Medical Research (ICMR), Hyderabad 156p.
- Gulia, S.K, Wilson, J.P., Carter, J. and Singh, B.P. (2007).Progress in grain pearl millet research and market development. Retrieved on 14th April 2012, from www.hort.purdue.edu/newcrop/ncnu07/pdfs/gulia1_96-203.pdf
- GoK, (Governmental of Kenya (2012).*Economic review of Agriculture.*Central Planning and Minting Unit. Government printer, Nairobi print.
- ICRISAT (1996): International Crops Research Institute for the Semi-Arid Tropics. [http://dSPACE.icrisat.ac.in/dSPACE/_12/12_2002.pdf] site visited on 6/8/2010.
- ICRISTAT (2008) Improved cultivation practices for Groundnut Technical Report.International Crops Research Institute for the semi-Arid Tropics.
- Karanja J, Ngulu SN, Mwangi G. (2009). The reaction of millet. Parasitism as influenced by nitrogen and Phosphorus fertilization. KASAL end of program Conference and exhibition, August, 2011. <http://www.kari.org/kasal>.
- Kari, (Kenya Agricultural Research Institute). (2007). Annual report 2006. Kari headquarters, Nairobi.
- Kari, (Kenya Agricultural Research Institute). (2008). Annual report 2007. Kari headquarters, Nairobi
- Kathari A., S.L. Kothari, R.K Satish Kumar, A. Vishnoi, K. Kothari, N. Watanabe (2005) Applications of biotechnology for improvement of millet crops: Review of progress and future prospects. *Plant Biotechnology* 22:81-88.
- Mnyenyembe P.H., and S.C. Gupta (1998) Variability for grain yield and related traits in Millet germplasm accessions from Malawi. *African Crop Science Journal* 6:317-322.

- Nagarajan, L. Smale, M. and Glewwe P. (2007). Determinants of Millet Diversity at the household-farm and village community levels in the dry lands of India: the role of local seed systems. *A journal of Agricultural Economics*, Vol. 36: pp. 157-167.
- National Research Council (1996). *List crops Africa vol 1*. Grain national academy press Washington. National Population Commission (NPC) (2006) *Nigerian Population Census Report*. National Population Commission, Abuja, 21-27
- N.P.C. CENSUS, 2006. National Population Commission Bio - data
- Obilana AB., E.O. Manyasa, J.G kibuka, and S. Ajanga (2002) *Finger Millet Blast Sample Collection in Kenya: Passport Data, Analyses of Disease Incidence and Report of Activities*. NARO, Uganda-ICRISAT HR, UK-KARI, Kakamega, ICRISAT-Nairobi. 12pp
- Oduri C.A.O (2008) *opportunities and Constraints for farmers for farmers of west africa to use seasonal precipitation forecast with Burkina faso*.
- Tayler J.R.N., TJ. Schober and S.R. Bean (2006) *Novel food and non-food uses for sorghum and millets*. *Journal of Cereal Science* 44:252 271.
- United State Agency for International development (2010). *Staple food value chain analysis canly repeat Kenya*. Retrieved on 24 June (2011).